

8T – Homomorphism's

"I know what it means to know something." Richard Feynman.

O Manor

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Abstract:

By analyzing the main features of the 8T it is possible to derive the homomorphic features of the theory in two contexts, that is a loss of information. The first loss of information is a result of prime pairs vanishing into zero, we can not correlate which zero to which prime pair. The second loss of information is part of a net variation composition leading to an higher prime, i.e. unique Boson. There could be more than one composition of lower magnitude primes which are creating the same element. Up to equation (2.16) is introduction.

Introduction

The 8T setting is a Lorentz manifold, $s = (M, g)$, with (3,1) signature. The manifold is the connected manifold, invoked stationary, $s = s_0 \times \mathbb{R}$. The manifold has areas of extremum curvatures that remain as they are overtime, this are yielding time invariant acceleration from them on the matrix tensor M, given by two conditions below (1). The reason for the acceleration in the 8T is that the manifold is a part of an infinite packet of universes, which interact at areas of extremum curvatures, as g is the Ricci flow, and as a result flatten each other matrix tensor causing it to accelerate in a time invariant rate, given by equations (1.2) and (1.1). By (1.2) those manifolds are topologically invariant. Flatness is an immediate result of this framework as given by the illustration below.

$$\frac{\partial \ell}{\partial s} \frac{\partial s}{\partial M} \frac{\partial M}{\partial g} \frac{\partial g}{\partial t} - \frac{\partial \ell}{\partial s'} \frac{\partial s'}{\partial M} \frac{\partial M}{\partial g'} \frac{\partial^2 g'}{\partial t^2} = 0 \quad (1)$$

$$\frac{\partial g}{\partial t} = 0 \cap \frac{\partial^2 g'}{\partial t^2} = 0$$

$$\frac{\partial \ell}{\partial s_1} - \sum_{n=2}^{\infty} \frac{\partial \ell}{\partial s_n} = 0 \quad (1.1)$$

$$\frac{\partial \ell}{\partial s_1} \frac{\partial s_1}{\partial M} \frac{\partial M}{\partial g} \frac{\partial g}{\partial t} - \sum_{n=2}^{\infty} \frac{\partial \ell}{\partial s_n} \frac{\partial s_n}{\partial M} \frac{\partial M}{\partial g} \frac{\partial g}{\partial t} = 0 \quad (1.2)$$

The manifold experience arbitrary amount of net curvature isomorphic to prime numbers or the number one. That construction yielded the primorial coupling constants series presented in equations (1.4) to (1.43) present the first and second representation. I.e. net curvature on the matrix tensor and the prime critical line.

$$F_{V=0} = 8 + (1) \tag{1.4}$$

$$F_R\# = \left(8 * \prod_{V=1}^{V=R} N_V + (3) \right) + N_V = 30:128:850:9254.. \tag{1.41}$$

$$N_V = 2 \left(V + \frac{1}{2} \right); V \geq 0 \tag{1.42}$$

$$N_V \in \mathbb{P} \cup (+1); \mathbb{P} \rightarrow \text{Set of Primes}$$

$$N_V = P_{max} \in [0, \mathbb{R}] \cup (+1); P_{max} \in \mathbb{P}$$

$$8 + (1)$$

$$[(8 * 3) + (3)] + 3 \rightarrow \left[2N_1 + \frac{1}{2} \right] + \frac{1}{2}$$

$$[(24 * 5) + (3)] + 5 \rightarrow \left[2N_2 + \frac{1}{2} \right] + \frac{1}{2}$$

$$[(120 * 7) + (3)] + 7 \rightarrow \left[2N_3 + \frac{1}{2} \right] + \frac{1}{2}$$

$$8 + (1): (24 + (3)) + 3: (120 + (3)) + 5: (840 + (3)) + 7 ... \tag{1.43}$$

For example, the Electromagnetic coupling term, we have proven the invariant three to be an electron by putting it in the fine structure constant formula:

$$[(24 * 5) + (3)] + 5 \rightarrow [(24 * 5) + (e)] + \gamma \quad (1.44)$$

We have described the arbitrary variations of the manifold by the term on the main equation:

$$\frac{\partial \mathcal{L}}{\partial s} \frac{\partial s}{\partial M} \frac{\partial M}{\partial g} \frac{\partial g}{\partial t} \delta g - \frac{\partial \mathcal{L}}{\partial s'} \frac{\partial s'}{\partial M} \frac{\partial M}{\partial g'} \frac{\partial^2 g'}{\partial t^2} \delta g' = 0 \quad (1.46)$$

We partitioned and discretized the arbitrary variation term and derived the existence of Fermion. In particular, we have shown that it must have an even amount of elements, which differ in sign and create nine threefold combination, and no more than two distinct elements.

$$\delta g_1 + \delta g_2 \dots = \sum_{i=1}^N \delta g_i \quad (1.47)$$

$$\sum_{i=1}^N \delta g_i = 0 \quad (1.48)$$

In addition, with bosons, described by the term (1.49) as they were proven discrete amount of prime curvature on the matric tensor:

$$\sum_{i=1}^M \delta g_i > 0 \quad (1.49)$$

We have presented the spin classification in the 8T thesis, page seventeen, while using the prime critical line:

Spin 0: $2N_0$ variations

Spin $\frac{1}{2}$: $2N_0 + 3$ variations

Spin 1: $2N_0 + 3 + N_V$ variations

Spin $N = 2N_0 + 3 + N_{V1} + N_{V2} \dots$ variations

The subject of analysis of the paper is the features of a theory in means for retaining information about certain processes that appears in it, the feature of retaining information will be analyzed via the idea of homomorphism. The first process is the process of prime pairs vanishing into zero, thus contributing to our vacuum. In the 8T, we derived the primordial by using total variations pairing, we searched for pairs that have certain features we know about fermions. In particular, the total sums of the pairs had to be two and three divisible. Below marked in black are the pairings we used to derive the series.

$$\begin{aligned} & (3,3) (3,5) (3,7) (3,11), (3,13) \dots \\ & (5,3) (5,5) (5,7) (5,11) \mathbf{(5,13)} \dots \\ & (7,3) (7,5) (7,7) \mathbf{(7,11)} (7,13) \dots \\ & \dots \\ & (29,19)(29,23), (29,29), \mathbf{(29,31)} \dots \end{aligned}$$

We calculated the sums of those prime pairing using the simple formula:

$$\sum_{i=1}^{i=N} \mathcal{P}_i = S; \quad (2.14)$$

$$N = 2$$

And each of those pairs to theorized based on theorem three, have a net curvature element proportional to the average, we searched for the first two pairs, derived the third coupling term using the formula of the primorial, without the prime pairing, and concluded the idea was correct.

$$(p_1, p_2) = (5, 13) \rightarrow N_V = +1$$

$$(p_3, p_4) = (29, 31) \rightarrow N_V = +3$$

$$(p_5, p_6) = (?, ?) \rightarrow N_V = +5$$

The fact that those prime pairs are in agreement with the coupling magnitudes does not mean that those pairs are exclusive or special. There is no law suggesting that these are the only pairs appearing in our theory and that is a positive thing. Therefore, all prime pairing are appearing but because we have the condition of (1.48) those prime pairs of variations are taken to vanish. Therefore, we can define the prime pairs that are not suitable for the coupling criteria:

$$\begin{aligned} (p_N, p_{N+K}) &= S_N \\ S_N &\neq S \\ [2, 3] &| S \end{aligned} \quad (2.15)$$

Assuming we required the original condition, for the sum to be divisible by two and three. Therefore, the majority of those pairs do not answer the condition. However since the still vanish due to being an even number and using equation, each pair could be regarded as a single distinct zero. So those prime pairs vanishing are the playing the rule of the vacuum in the 8T.

$$\begin{aligned} \sum_{N=7}^{\infty} (p_N, p_{N+K}) &\rightarrow \sum_{i=1}^T 0_i \\ T &\rightarrow \infty \end{aligned}$$

The summation of the prime pairing to zero is resulting in an infinite set of zeros. That is synonymous with the vacuum idea of quantum field theory, all the prime pairs, which do not have net variation element, that is non-vanishing element, N_V , are the composite of the vacuum of the 8T:

$$\sum_{i=1}^T 0_i = \mathcal{V} \quad (2.16)$$

Up to this point was introduction, reader is probability familiar with every equation presented, as those are 8T fundamentals. **From here** on out, we have a completely **new paper**. Suppose we have a new zero appears, that zero could be a result of two distinct prime pairs, in that sense we don't have an isomorphism but an homomorphism which indicate a loss for information.

$$0_{i=1} \rightarrow (p_{N=1}, p_{N=2})$$

$$0_{i=1} \rightarrow (p_{N=3}, p_{N=4})$$

The loss of information in that sense is indicating that the arrow of time is not reversible, that is because it is impossible to indicate to which pair the zero is correlated. Additional feature of loss of information is part of the primordial higher primes which composite of lower magnitude primes. In the proof of the Riemann hypothesis, author showed that primes are forming non-abelian group under addition and multiplication. The condition under addition is to have odd amount of higher primes, to reach new higher prime. Since prime are isomorphic to a Boson, we create a unique prime in more than one combination. Take as an example the prime, i.e. Boson $N_{V_4} = +101$, the first prime composition is:

$$N_{V_4} = 91 + 7 + 3$$

The second composition is an example:

$$N_{V_4} = 31 + 67 + 3$$

There are several unique compositions for distinct higher primes, which indicate that it is impossible to correlate an higher Bosons to a constant structure, that is in fact a major feature of gravity in the 8T, and the reason we consider it to be a time variant interaction.

$$[(2N_{gravity}) + (3)] + N_{V_1} + N_{V_2} + N_{V_3} = \left[2N_{gravity} + \frac{1}{2}\right] + \frac{1}{2} + \frac{1}{2} + \frac{1}{2} \quad (2.2)$$

$$[2N_{gravity} + 2] \rightarrow [2N_{gravity}] \quad (2.3)$$

$$[(2N_0) + (3)] + N_{VK1} + N_{VK2} + N_{VK3}$$

$$[N_{VK1}, N_{VK2}, N_{VK3}] \in \mathbb{P}$$

$$K1 \dots KN \in \mathbb{R}$$

$$[(2N_0) + (3)] + N_{VK1} + N_{VK2} + N_{VK4}$$

$$N_{VK3} \neq N_{VK4}$$

The structure of the gravity is invariant to the change of the element. Since the total spin is invariant, i.e. two, there is not a change in the nature of gravity; the structure is the same while the composite element could be different.

$$[(2N_0) + (3)] + N_{VK1} + N_{VK2} + N_{VK3} \rightarrow 2N_0 + 2$$

$$[(2N_0) + (3)] + N_{VK1} + N_{VK2} + N_{VK4} \rightarrow 2N_0 + 2$$

Summing up, we have defined two kinds of homomorphism in the paper; the first is from prime pairs to zero:

$$\mathcal{U}: S_N \rightarrow 0_i \quad (2.18)$$

The second is from lower composition of primes to reach a distinct higher prime:

$$Z: \sum_{K=1}^N N_{VK} \rightarrow N_{V(K1+K2\dots)} \quad (2.19)$$

$$N = 2n + 1;$$

$$n \in \mathbb{R}$$

Those two process are positive indication that the arrow of time is not reversible and that there is constant "loss" of information as the manifold develops. Lost in a sense that it is impossible to retrace how we reached a certain situation, not lost in a sense that some net variation has vanished from the manifold, we have presented the conservation of variation to eliminate such scenarios.

References

- [1] O. Manor. "8 Theory – The Theory of Everything" In: (2021)

Manor Ohad